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The Perception of the Financial Situation of European Consumers

Between January and October 2022 it decreased by 138% on average for the countries analyzed

Eurostat calculates the value of the financial situation in the last 12 months. This is an indicator that is part of the surveys that Eurostat conducts as part of the description of consumer behavior and expectations. The indicator, therefore, represents the change in the financial situation perceived in the last 12 months.

Ranking of European countries by value of financial situation in the last 12 months as of October 2022. Finland ranks first in value of financial situation in the last 12 months with an amount equal to -4.7, followed by Germany with a value equal to -13.2 and from Latvia with an amount equal to -14.1 units. In the middle of the ranking are the following countries: Serbia with an amount equal to -26.1%, followed by Ireland with an amount equal to -27.5% and Italy equal to an amount equal to -27.7%. Hungary closes the ranking with an amount equal to -43.7%, followed by North Macedonia with an amount of -48.1% and Greece equal to an amount of -55.5%.

Ranking countries by value of percent change in financial condition over the past 12 months between January 2022 and October 2022. Turkey ranks first in value of percent change in financial condition over the past 12 months between January 2022 and October 2022 with a value of to +8% equal to an amount of 3.8 units, followed by Latvia with an amount of -19% equal to an amount of -2.3 units and by Slovakia for an amount equal to -49% equal to an amount of -8.2 units. In the middle of the table are Portugal with an amount equal to -125% equal to an amount of -17.9 units, followed by Croatia with an amount equal to -148% equal to a value of -9.9 units, and by Italy with a value equal to -172% equal to an amount of -17.5 units. Germany closes the ranking with a value equal to -925% equal to an amount of 14.8 units, followed by Ireland with an amount equal to -1096% equal to an amount of 25.2 units and by Denmark with a value equal to -1103% equal to an amount of 35.3%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. The clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized through the use of the Elbow method is presented below. The following clusters were then obtained, i.e.:

- Cluster 1: Bulgaria, Spain, Portugal, Czech Republic, Cyprus, Slovenia, Estonia, Netherlands, Hungary;
- Cluster 2: Greece, Turkey, North Macedonia;
- Cluster 3: Belgium, Croatia, Luxembourg, Poland, France, Serbia, Montenegro, Austria, Albania, Latvia, Denmark, Italy, Malta, Slovakia, Ireland;
- Cluster 4: Sweden, Finland, Germany, Lithuania;

Analyzing the median of the clusters, it is possible to identify the following ordering, namely: C4=-15.55>C3=-22.7>C1=-32.7>C2=-48.1. From a geographical point of view, it appears that the value of the perception of the financial condition is higher in the Scandinavian countries, while Greece and Turkey are in the last places.

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Network analysis with Manhattan distance. An analysis using the Manhattan distance is presented below. There are two network structures of which one is complex and one is simplified. The complex network structure is made up as follows, namely:

- Slovakia has a connection with Italy for an amount equal to 0.51 units and with France for a value equal to 0.63 units;
- Albania has a connection with France with an amount equal to 0.50 units and with Italy with an amount equal to 0.62 units;
- Italy has a connection with Slovakia for an amount equal to 0.51 units, with Albania for a value equal to 0.62 units, with France for a value equal to 0.44 units and with Croatia for an amount of 0.61 units;
- France has a connection with Slovakia with a value of 0.63 units, with Albania with a value of 0.5 units, with Italy with a value of 0.44 units, with Belgium for a value equal to 0.56 units and with Croatia for a value equal to 0.45 units;
- Croatia has a connection with France worth 0.45 units, with Italy worth 0.61 units, with Belgium worth 0.58 units, and with Luxembourg worth 0.61 units value equal to 0.62 units;
- Belgium has a connection with France worth 0.56, with Croatia worth 0.58, with Serbia worth 0.56 and with Poland worth value equal to 0.43 units;
- Serbia has a connection with Belgium for a value equal to 0.56 units and with Poland for a value equal to 0.48 units;
- Poland has a connection with Belgium worth 0.43 units, and with Serbia worth 0.48 units;
- Luxembourg has a connection with Croatia worth 0.62 units.

There is also a further simplified network structure set up as follows:

- Slovenia and Portugal are connected with a value of 0.6 units.

The analysis shows that the nation that has the greatest connection with other countries is France. This network structure can be better understood by considering the propagation effects. For example, if the French population believes at a certain point that their financial condition is starting to worsen, this behavior would also spread internationally, affecting first of all Slovakia, and then Belgium, Albania, Croatia and Italy. In other words, the network analysis makes it possible to identify the effects of propagation of the variation in the financial perception of consumers in European countries.

Conclusions. Considering the average of the values between January 2022 and October 2022, it appears that the financial perception of Europeans relating to the last 12 months has significantly decreased from an amount of -11.4% to a value of -27.1% or a change equal to -15.7 equal to an amount of -138%. It should be considered that already in January 2022 the financial perception was already significantly negative with an amount equal to a value of -11.4. Certainly this condition is due to a set of factors or covid19, increase in the price of energy, increase in inflation, Russian-Ukrainian conflict. An adverse macro-economic condition that has reduced the financial situation of Europeans and their consideration of the recent 12-month financial situation of consumers. Since about 80% of GDP is made up of consumption, in upper-middle income countries, it follows that the worsening of financial perception, even if directed towards the recent past, can have a negative impact on the probability of growth in the Gross Domestic Product of European countries and Italy. In other words, the network analysis makes it possible to identify the effects of propagation of the variation in the financial perception of consumers in European countries.

Declarations

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Appendix

